

LUNAR SEISMOGRAPH ONBOARD THE CHANG'E-7 MISSION AND ITS GROUND EXPERIMENTS. X. Y. Zhu¹, C.L. Li¹, W. Zuo¹ and W. L. Chen¹, ¹National Astronomical Observatories, Chinese Academy of Science, Beijing, China.

Introduction: Chang'e-7 is China's most sophisticated robotic lunar mission to date, involving orbiting, landing, roving, and hopping spacecraft. Scheduled for launch in 2026, this mission will target the lunar south pole, a region of immense scientific and strategic interest[1]. Chang'e-7 lunar lander will deploy China's first independently developed lunar seismograph on the surface of the lunar south pole. The lunar seismograph will provide situ measurements of ground motions generated by moonquakes and meteoroid impacts. Experiment on ground is an important tool for performance evaluation of onboard payload. A series of ground experiments are performed to evaluate the performance of lunar seismograph.

Instrument description: The Chang'e-7 Lunar Seismograph is a high-precision instrument designed for detecting lunar seismic waveforms. Its internal structure comprises two sets of three-component seismometers—a broadband seismometer and a short-period Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) seismometer—totaling six data channels. This configuration enables the measurement of seismic data along three orthogonal axes: two horizontal axes (X and Y) and one vertical axis (Z). The combination of these two seismometer types allows for broadband detection of both low-frequency and high-frequency lunar seismic signals, achieving complementarity in both frequency band and dynamic range.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the overall block diagram of the seismometer shows that the two seismometer units, together with an internal Electronics Unit (EU), form the complete instrument. The seismometer connects via cables to the Chang'e-7 Payload Management Unit (PMU), which provides power supply, facilitates data transmission, and executes control command for the instrument.

Figure1 Functional Block Diagram of the Chang'E-7 Lunar seismograph

Both the broadband seismometer and the MEMS seismometer operate based on a spring-mass system for seismic detection. When seismic signals propagate to the instrument, inertial forces cause displacement of the proof mass. This displacement is converted into a collectible voltage signal from the external acceleration input using capacitive displacement sensing. Furthermore, negative feedback is employed to optimize the system's response, thereby achieving wider bandwidth, larger dynamic range, and superior linearity. The technical specifications of the Chang'e-7 Lunar Seismograph are listed in the following table[2].

No.	Parameter	Specification	
		Broadband Seismometer	MEMS Seismometer
1	Measurement Bandwidth	1/120 ~10Hz	1 ~ 100 Hz
2	Magnitude Measurement Range	-4 to +3.2	-3.2 to +4
3	Acceleration Measurement Range	2.5ng~2.5mg	16ng~16mg
4	Self-Noise	<2.5ng/√Hz @1Hz	<16ng/√Hz @10Hz
5	Sensitivity Calibration Error	≤ 3%	≤ 3%
6	Dynamic Range	> 120dB	> 120dB
7	Sensitivity	2000 ±60V/g	187 ±20V/g

Ground Experiment: Two ground experiments were designed to evaluate the performance of the lunar seismograph on the lunar surface. The first experiment was a natural seismic event detection test. The lunar seismograph was co-located with a high-precision commercial seismometer, the Trillium Horizon 120. Natural earthquake events were used as excitation sources. The lunar seismograph and the reference seismometer simultaneously detected these natural earthquakes. By comparing and analyzing the data generated by both instruments, in conjunction with the natural earthquake parameters published by the national seismic network, the data quality of the lunar seismograph was evaluated. Representative teleseismic and local seismic events were selected for the test. Through waveform comparison and correlation coefficient calculation, the detection performance of the lunar seismograph was quantitatively assessed. The comparative test using two natural seismic events—a teleseism (magnitude 5.8) and a local event (magnitude 3.2)—yielded the following results: The three-component waveforms from the broadband seismometer and the reference instrument showed a high degree of consistency, with maximum correlation coefficients for P-waves, S-waves, and surface waves reaching 0.995, 0.979, and 0.982, respectively. Within the overlapping frequency band of 1-10 Hz, the waveforms from the broadband seismometer and the MEMS seismometer were also in good agreement, with maximum correlation coefficients reaching 0.915, 0.939, and 0.976, respectively. These results verified the lunar seismograph's capability to capture weak, broadband teleseismic signals and high-frequency local seismic signals, confirming its reliable data quality and performance highly consistent with that of high-precision commercial seismometers.

The second experiment was an in-orbit working condition verification test for the lunar seismograph. When deployed on the lunar surface, the seismograph is gently lowered by a release mechanism under the Moon's gravity. Due to the lunar topography, the seismograph may end up in a non-horizontal position and may not be in tight contact

with the surface. To assess the degree of coupling between the seismograph and the lunar surface and its impact on monitoring moonquakes, an in-orbit working condition verification test was conducted on Earth. In this test, under vibration conditions induced by the same source, the recorded data from the lunar seismograph placed on loose, uncompacted lunar regolith simulant was compared with data from a commercial seismometer placed on manually compacted and leveled lunar regolith simulant. This comparison aimed to analyze the influence of the coupling state between the seismograph and the simulant lunar soil on moonquake monitoring. During the experiment, the working tilt angle of the seismograph was adjusted by placing stones underneath it. The results of the in-orbit working condition verification test showed that when the in-orbit working tilt angle of the seismograph was less than 20° , the waveform correlation coefficient between the lunar seismograph and the reference seismometer exceeded 0.94. This verified that the lunar seismograph can consistently and reliably acquire high-quality lunar seismic data even under complex coupling conditions with the lunar regolith simulant and at various tilt angles less than 20° .

References:

- [1] WANG C. et al.(2024) *National Science Review*,11(2): nwad329.
- [2]Wen Z. et al. (2026) *Chinese Journal of Space Science*,doi:10.11728/cjss2025-0121